

ISic2724

I.Sicily inscription 2724

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Leontini

Place of origin (modern)

Lentini

Provenance

Necropolis

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lentini, Museo Archeologico di
Lentini

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI333199

1. [Καλ]λικ-

2. ράτης.

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645144

EDCS 70900863

PHI 333199

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 45.1376

Manganaro, G. 1995. Sikelika I. *Quaderni Urbinati di Cultura Classica*. 49. At 98 fig.21

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Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 339

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